

THE EFFECT OF THE UNIVERSAL FEED ADDITIVE “PROBIOKORM” ON THE RABBITS’ ORGANISM

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Abstract. Biotechnology and biotechnology sectors (agricultural biotechnology, food industry biotechnology, pharmaceutical biotechnology) serve to meet the needs of the population. In particular, the development of rabbit farming in agriculture, obtaining dietary meat products and raw materials for highquality fur from rabbits is of practical importance in providing the population with food products. Therefore, the study of the physiological indicators of the rabbit organism, the dynamics of their development and the study of factors affecting the growth intensity of rabbits are among the current issues.

Keywords: Probiokorm, rabbit, protein, amino acid, probiotic.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the growth intensity of rabbits is directly related to the feed environment they consume and nutritional conditions. In this regard, many rabbit farms consider it preferable to enrich the rabbit diet with universal nutritional supplements (probiotics) to increase its productivity [1,2]. It has been scientifically proven that probiotics effectively affect the physiological parameters of the rabbit body (body weight, hematological parameters, intestinal microflora, growth dynamics, etc.), thereby increasing its productivity [3,4,5]. In addition, sources indicate that the use of probiotics

helps to optimize metabolic processes in the rabbit body, effectively affects the protein-amino acid status and morphological, physiological and biochemical parameters of rabbits [6,7,8].

In this regard, studying the effect of probiotic supplements on the growth and development of rabbits is of both theoretical and practical importance.

The purpose of the study. Study of the dynamics of growth and development of young rabbits under the influence of the universal nutritional supplement “ProBioKorm”.

Results and their analysis. Probiotics are not only a nutritional supplement for rabbits, but also a pharmacological treatment [2, 5, 6]. Many sources have reported that under their influence, the physiological indicators of the rabbit’s body change in a positive direction, and their development dynamics are sharply affected [10].

It is known that full-fledged feeding of rabbits is the main factor in their high survival and live weight indicators. In our studies, the feed ration was enriched with the universal nutritional supplement “ProBioKorm”. We studied the

dynamics of body weight of young rabbits at 21, 30, 45, 60, and 90 days of age.

In the studies, we can see that the body weight of newborn rabbit babies in groups I and II was 53.1 ± 0.01 and 54.7 ± 0.01 , respectively.

In the experiments, adding the liquid probiotic “ProBioKorm” to water had a positive effect on the physiological indicators of rabbits, leading to an increase in body weight. In the experiments, the rabbits of the II group, which received the probiotic, were superior to the control group in terms of growth and development indicators at all periods. In particular, the live weight of the rabbits of the 21-day-old group in the experimental group was 466.0 ± 0.03 , while the figure was 509.0 ± 0.015 in the animals of the control group. The results obtained show that the addition of the probiotic “ProBioKorm” to the feed ration of the animals of the I-control group (feed ration (MKR)) increased the weight of the animals of the I-control group by 43 grams (9.2%) compared to the control group. The increase in body weight intensity of rabbits increased in accordance with the dynamics of their growth periods (30 days, 45 days, 60 days, 90 days). That is, the live weight of the control group was 30 days (665.3 ± 0.02), 45 days (1015.8 ± 0.04), 60 days (1390.0 ± 0.03) and 90 days (2152.2 ± 0.11) of the rabbits, while these indicators were 30 days (711.0 ± 0.03), 45 days (1072.0 ± 0.015), 60 days (1470.0 ± 0.02) and 90 days (2277.4 ± 0.012) in the experimental animals of group II (feed diet (MKR + “ProBioKorm”).

These statistical data indicate that the probiotic “ProBioKorm” effectively affected the physiological indicators of rabbits, leading to an increase in their body weight clearly proves. The intensity of body weight gain increased in accordance with the dynamics of growth periods (30 days (6.8%), 45 days (5.6%), 60 days (5.7%), 90 days (5.8%). In general, the increase in body weight of rabbits in the experimental groups was in accordance with the dynamics of growth periods (their live weight at birth increased by (1.6 g), at 21 days (43.0 g), at 30 days (45.7 g), at 45 days (56.2), at 60 days (80.0 g), at 90 days (125.4 g) and every 15 days by 5.8% < 9.2%) and prevailed.

From these results, we can see that the increase in body weight of young rabbits under the influence of the probiotic “ProBioKorm” increased their initial indicators in accordance with the period of their growth and affected the dynamics of growth. It can be said that the nutritional supplements contained in the probiotic

“ProBioKorm” actively affected the physiological indicators of the rabbits' body and led to an increase in their body weight.

In general, in the above studies, the body weight and development dynamics of young rabbits under the influence of the universal nutritional supplement “ProBioKorm” in the feed ration showed that the daily live weight gain was higher in all periods compared to the control group. This is directly related to the fact that the universal nutritional supplement “ProBioKorm” consists of various vitamins, various strains of pure microorganisms, or has a therapeutic effect.

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